

SPEAKING RELATED FACTORS AND THE SPOKEN DISCOURSE COMPETENCE OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Communication is and has always been one of the fundamental needs of human beings. With its primary goals to get and share information from a speaker to the listener, this has become very crucial in the aspect of living. In this modern society and globalization era we are living in, mastering English as a language is very important. This study aimed to determine the relationship of spoken discourse competence and the factors affecting the speaking performance in English of Grade 10 students. Descriptive-Correlational design was utilized in the study participated by thirty-four (34) Grade 10 students. A teacher-made survey questionnaire was conducted online via google forms, and a rubric was used in scoring students speaking performance. Mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage and Pearson product moment of correlation were the statistical treatments used. Based on the findings, the test of correlation shows that there is no enough statistical evidence to support the claim between the speaking performance related factors and their spoken discourse competence since only two indicators from the speaking performance related factors are significantly related to their spoken discourse competence. However, there is a positive relationship between the Affective Factors in terms of Anxiety and the Spoken Discourse Competence in terms of Cohesiveness. Whereas, there is a negative relationship between the Linguistic factors in terms of Fluency and the Spoken Discourse Competence in terms of Cohesiveness. Moreover, the results suggest that although fluency and coherence or cohesion are two different ideas, both of these are important to give a clear and organized presentation. Furthermore, an individual needs to speak in a natural flow and give a structurally organized message as a whole. With these implications in the educative process, teachers are highly recommended to give various speaking performance tasks to identify learners' capabilities in speaking the language.

Keywords: Spoken Discourse Competence, Speaking Performance Related Factors, Thematic Instruction